

ADSORPTION AND CHEMISORPTION METHODS FOR PURIFICATION OF GAS FROM HALOGEN AND ACID SALTS.

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Annotation: The article classifies the purification of acid salts and halogens in oil and gas products by adsorption and chemisorption methods.

Keywords: purification from fluorine compounds, chemisorbents, regeneration, fluorite, sorbent, lignin and calcium lignosulfate, iron chloride, hydrogen sulfide, chemisorption purification.

Purification of fluorine compounds

Chemisorption and ion exchange methods are used.

The following are used as chemisorbents : limestone, alumogels , nepheline syenites, sodium fluoride.

Figure 25 shows the scheme of chemisorption purification of exhaust gases from hydrogen fluoride on limestone. The process temperature is more than 350 °C, the contact time of the gas with the sorbent is at least 7.6 s. CaF_2 is formed on the surface of CaCO_3 , after which the sorbent is unloaded onto a screen, where it is subjected to dispersion. Detachable CaF_2 (fluorite) (passes under the sieve) is a commercial product. The cleaning efficiency reaches 95%.

Рис.25
 Схема установки для хемосорбции фторида водорода известняком: 1 — бункер; 2 — корпус контактного аппарата; 3 — газораспределительное устройство; 4 — пневматический эжектор

For finer purification, ion exchange methods are used on anion exchangers, regeneration is carried out with solutions of sodium or ammonium hydroxide.

Purification of chlorine and hydrogen chloride

To remove chlorine and hydrogen chloride from exhaust gases, adsorption methods are used using the following sorbents:

Component to be removed	Sorbent
Chlorine	Lignin and calcium lignosulfate - large-tonnage wastes of chemical processing of wood and other plant materials
hydrogen chloride	Iron chloride, $\text{CuCl}+\text{MgO}$, CuSO_4 , CdSO_4 , $\text{Cu}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$, $\text{Pb}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$, organic polymeric materials, zeolites, blast furnace and steel-smelting slags, ash from municipal waste incineration (all listed wastes have $\text{pH}>7$), activated carbons, silica gels, anion exchangers

Рис.26 Башня сухой очистки газов гидроксидом железа (1 — слой сорбента; 2 — опорная решетка)

Purification from hydrogen sulfide .

Usually, the content of H₂S in the exhaust gases is low; adsorption on Fe(OH)₃, activated carbons, and zeolites is used to remove it.

Figure 26 shows an apparatus for the process of chemisorption purification from hydrogen sulfide on swamp ore containing Fe₂O₃ mixed with sawdust. The reactions that take place in this process are:

thus, iron (III) hydroxide binds sulfur into sulfide, which in the presence of atmospheric oxygen is oxidized to zero oxidation state. After the

accumulation of sulfur in the sorbent in the amount of 40-50%, the sorbent is unloaded and subjected to firing, the resulting sulfur dioxide is sent to the production of sulfuric acid.

Рис.27 . Схема установки очистки газа синтетическими цеолитами: 1 — компрессор; 2 — адсорберы; 3 — теплообменник

Chemisorption purification from hydrogen sulfide on activated carbons in the presence of atmospheric oxygen is also possible, taking place in accordance with the reactions:

The disadvantage is the possibility of ignition of activated carbon.

To remove hydrogen sulfide, sorption on synthetic zeolites (CaA , NaA , NaX) is used. Zeolites catalyze the oxidation of hydrogen sulfide to elemental sulfur, the process is carried out at a temperature of 315 ° C, at this temperature sulfur is released in the form of vapors, which are then condensed and burned to produce sulfur dioxide.

REFERENCES:

1. Mukhametgaliev I. M. et al. Purification of gases from acidic components // Bulletin of the Kazan Technological University. - 2017. - T. 20. - No. 3.
2. Tursunov B. Zh., Gaibullaev S. A., Zhumaev K. K. Influence of technological parameters on glycol gas dehydration //MEDICAL SCIENCES. - 2020. - Vol. 1. - No. 55. - P. 33.
3. Gaibullaev S. A., Tursunov B. Zh., Timurov Sh. M. TECHNOLOGY GTL-DIRECTION FOR OBTAINING FUEL IMPROVED ENVIRONMENTAL PROPERTIES //Theory and practice of modern science. – 2019. – no. 6. - S. 168-172.
4. Zaripov G. B., Gaibullaev S. A. Choice of operating mode for the process of low-temperature separation of hydrocarbon raw materials // Young scientist. – 2016. – no. 3. - S. 98-100.
5. Imaev S.Z., Voitenkov E.V. Promising technologies for extracting acidic components from natural gases // Oilfield business. – 2013. – no. 4. - S. 17-23.
6. Gaibullaev S. A., Tursunov B. Zh. PYROCONDENSATE - THE MOST IMPORTANT RAW MATERIAL OF CHEMICAL SYNTHESIS // Universum : technical sciences. – 2020. – no. 6-2(75).
7. Kuandykov E. S., Islamutdinova A. A., Daminev R. R. A method for cleaning hydrocarbon gas of acidic components //BBK 72 A43. - 2017. - S. 131.

REFERENCES:

1. Mukhametgaliev IM et al. Gas cleaning from acid components // Bulletin of Kazan Technological University. - 2017. - T. 20. - No. 3.
2. Tursunov B. Zh ., Gaibullaev SA, Zhumaev KK Influence of technological parameters on glycol gas drying // MEDICAL SCIENCES. - 2020. - T. 1. - No. 55 . -- S. 33.
3. Gaibullaev SA, Tursunov B. Zh ., Timurov Sh. M. GTL TECHNOLOGYPROSPECTIVE DIRECTION OF OBTAINING FUELS WITH IMPROVED ECOLOGICAL PROPERTIES // Theory and practice of modern science. - 2019. - No. 6. - S. 168-172.
4. Zaripov GB, Gaibullaev SA Selection of the operating mode of the process of low-temperature separation of hydrocarbon raw materials // Young scientist. - 2016. - No. 3. - S. 98-100.

5. Imaev SZ, Voitenkov EV Perspective technologies of extraction of acid components from natural gases // Oilfield business. - 2013. - No. 4. - S. 17-23.
6. Gaibullaev SA, Tursunov B. Zh . PYROCONDENSATE - THE MOST IMPORTANT RAW MATERIAL OF CHEMICAL SYNTHESIS // Universum : technical sciences. - 2020. - No. 6-2
7. Kuandykov ES, Islamutdinova AA, Daminev RR Method of cleaning hydrocarbon gas of acid components // BBK 72 A43. - 2017 . -- S. 131.